

Analyst Administrator
Date Tuesday, May 17, 2022 11:53 AM

Sample Name	Description	Quality Checks
CAS-117-1 crystals_1	Sample 025 By Administrator Date Tuesday, May 17 2022	The Quality Checks give rise to a Weak Bands warning for the sample.